

STUDY OF BACTERIA WITH CELLULOLYTIC ACTIVITY IN UZBEKISTAN AND DETERMINATION OF CELLULOLYTIC ACTIVITY OF BACTERIA BELONGING TO THE BACILLUS GROUP

¹Bakhora Ismoilovna Turaeva, ²Guzal Jumaniyazovna Kutlieva, ³Xulkar Fozil qizi Kamolova, ⁴Azamjon Bakhodirovich Soliev

^{1,2,3}Institute of Microbiology of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, turaevabakhora@mail.ru

⁴Republican Scientific and Practical Center of Sports Medicine, Tashkent, UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. The conversion of cellulose to glucose occurs on the basis of a complex interaction between glycoside and hydrolase enzymes. As a result of the hydrolysis of glycosidic - 1,4 bonds, short chains of cellulose, oligodextrin, cellobiose, and gluconase are formed. Cellulolytic activity is determined by qualitative and quantitative methods. In studies, primary screening methods are performed by applying Congo red to agar media, but this method does not measure the amount of enzyme synthesized by the bacteria. Spectrophotometric research methods are based on the quantitative determination of reducing sugars formed by cellulose enzymes using specific and appropriate substrates. Filter paper is used to determine the total cellulolytic activity. The cellulolytic activity of bacteria depends not only on their species but also on the composition of the substrate, cultivation conditions, and the correct choice of parameters for enzymatic reactions. In our studies, the cellulolytic activity of bacteria living in the digestive systems of animals and insects is determined by spectrophotometric research methods.

Keywords: *Bacillus*, Carboxymethyl-cellulose (CM-Cellulose), cellulolytic activity, DEAE CMC, cellulolytic microorganisms, detection methods

Аннотация. Целлюлозанинг глюкозага айланиши гликозид ва гидролаза ферментларининг мураккаб ўзаро таъсири асосида содир бўлади. Гликозид б-1,4 боғларнинг гидролизланиши натижасида целлюлоза, олигодекстрин, целлобиоза ва глюконазанинг қисқа занжирлари ҳосил бўлади. целлюлитик фаоллик сифат ва миқдорий усуллар билан аниқланади. Тадқиқотларда бирламчи скрининг усуллари Конго қизилини агар муҳитига қўлаш орқали амалга оширилди, аммо бу усул бактериялар томонидан синтез қилинган фермент миқдорини ўлчамайди. Спектрофотометрик тадқиқот усуллари аниқ ва тегишли субстратлар ёрдамида целлюлоза ферментлари таъсирида ҳосил бўлган қайтарувчи (камайтирувчи) қандларни миқдорий аниқлашга асосланган. Филтр қоғози умумий целлюлитик фаолликни аниқлаш учун ишлатилади. Бактерияларнинг целлюлитик фаоллиги нафақат уларнинг турларига, балки субстрат таркибига, этиштириши шароитларига, ферментатив реакциялар параметрларини тўғри танлашга ҳам боғлиқ. тадқиқотларимизда ҳайвонлар ва хашаротлар овқат ҳазм қилиш тизимида яшовчи бактерияларнинг целлюлитик фаоллиги Спектрофотометрик тадқиқот усуллари орқали аниқланди.

Калит сўзлар: *Bacillus*, карбоксиметилцеллюлоза (КМ-целлюлоза), целлюлитик фаоллик, ДЕАЕ КМС, целлюлитик микроорганизмлар, аниқлаш усуллари.

Аннотация. Превращение целлюлозы в глюкозу происходит на основе сложного взаимодействия ферментов гликозидов и гидролаз. В результате гидролиза гликозидных β-1,4-связей образуются короткие цепи целлюлозы, олигодекстрин, целлобиоза и глюконаза. целлюлитическую активность определяют качественными и количественными

методами. В исследованиях методы первичного скрининга выполнялись путем нанесения конго красного на агаровую среду, но этот метод не измеряет количество фермента, синтезируемого бактериями. Спектрофотометрические методы исследования основаны на количественном определении восстанавливающих сахаров, образуемых ферментами целлюлозы, с использованием конкретных и соответствующих субстратов. Фильтровальную бумагу используют для определения общей целлюлозолитической активности. Целлюлолитическая активность бактерий зависит не только от их вида, но и от состава субстрата, условий культивирования, правильного выбора параметров ферментативных реакций. В наших исследованиях целлюлозолитическую активность бактерий, обитающих в пищеварительной системе животных и насекомых, определяли спектрофотометрическими методами исследования.

Ключевые слова: *Bacillus*, карбоксиметилцеллюлоза (СМ-целлюлоза), целлюлозолитическая активность, ДЭАЭ КМС, целлюлозолитические микроорганизмы, методы детекции.

Cellulolytic bacteria synthesize cellulosic enzymes that hydrolyze cellulose into glucose. Cellulose production occurs due to a response to or direct association with cellulose in cells. Cellulose is an enzyme complex that forms a synergistic system, which gradually becomes an energy source in biomass [1]. According to world scientists, many types of microorganisms have cellulose biosynthesis. The reason why cellulolytic bacteria are widely used is that they are very numerous, produce fast and stable enzymes, produce high biomass, and have advantages such as rapid incubation. Therefore, until now, research has been carried out on the isolation and study of cellulolytic bacteria. Cellulose consists of glucose units linked by β -bonds and has unique properties. The most common natural sources of cellulose include paper, wheat bran, tree wood, straw, etc. In the digestive system of some ruminants, cellulose is digested by the development of certain cellulolytic bacteria [2]. Therefore, ruminant digestive tracts or gastric juice are the most common choice for the isolation of cellulolytic bacteria. Carboxymethylcellulose (CMC) is a common commercial source of cellulose. *Clostridium* cellulolytic is one of the cellulose-degrading bacteria that is widely used on an industrial scale. In a study, CMC (1 g/L) obtained on the basis of bacteria was used as an electron donor to generate electricity with a power density of up to 143 mW/m² [3]. This study aims to identify a potential strain of cellulolytic bacteria isolated from peat ecosystems. The used method is experimental and consists of successive stages: isolation and screening of cellulolytic bacteria, quantitative analysis of cellulose. Morphological and physiological characteristics were studied, identification was carried out using the Bergey detector, and studies were carried out on the basis of 7 isolates. As a result of screening, seven isolates of bacteria with cellulolytic activity were incubated in an agar medium with 1% carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC). *Bacillus*, *Lactobacillus*, and *Corynebacterium* strains showed high cellulolytic activity of 2.82 mm, 2.65 mm, and 2.47 mm. Cellulolytic activity is indicated by the haq value around colonies incubated after instillation of Congo red in nutrient medium containing 1% CMC [4]. The cellulolytic activity of free enzyme-synthesizing bacteria depends on the hydrolysis of cellulose to sugar under the action of enzymes on a specific lignocellulosic substrate. In general, it is explained by the presence of a cooperative or synergistic effect between at least three classes of free enzymes. The classification of cellulolytic bacteria is divided into groups of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria according to their oxygen requirement. Satheesh Kumar et al. [5] *Bacillus* sp.

determined the cellulolytic activity of a bacterial strain, created optimal conditions for the synthesis of cellulolytic enzymes, and used filter paper and cellulose powder as substrates in a liquid nutrient medium. Isolation and screening of cellulose-degrading bacteria from termites and bookworms is performed by inoculating filter paper in a liquid nutrient medium. Cellulose-degrading bacteria are identified based on the results of the turbidity of the enriched nutrient medium and the softening of the filter paper [6]. Cellulose has the most durable and stable structure. Hydrogen bonds between the hydroxyl groups of cellulose fibrils, called microfibrils and microfibrils, and Van der Waals forces provide the necessary structure of cellulose fibers for glucose particles. Rabbit and chicken stomach samples were taken. Samples were also taken from the bark-dwelling Corroid beetle and the termite, which feeds on cellulose. In the next step of the study, it was cleaned with 3% hydrogen peroxide, alcohol, and distilled water. Cleaned samples were cultured in meat peptone broth (MRS) media prepared under sterile laboratory conditions. For the isolation of pure cultures of bacteria, a cultivation method generally accepted in microbiology was used on meat peptone agar (GPA) medium [7]. Based on primary screening, bacterial strains with cellulolytic activity were selected [8]. Morphological and physiological characteristics of pure isolates were determined and identified according to Bergey [9, 10]. The determination of cellulase enzyme activity in the culture liquid of selected bacterial strains with high cellulolytic activity was carried out according to the modified method of Mendels and Weber [11, 12]. The activity of the cellulase enzyme was determined in the supernatant of the suspension of the culture fluid of bacterial strains at a concentration of 10^{8-9} spores/mL. Cotton fiber was taken as a substrate to determine exoglucanase activity. 1 ml of bacterial liquid supernatant was taken, 50 mg of defatted cotton wool was placed in a test tube, and 1 ml of 0.2 M acetate buffer pH 5.5 was added. The reaction mixture was incubated at 50°C for 1 h. The amount of reducing sugar was determined by the Somoji-Nelson method. 1 mL of Somoji solution was added to the incubation mixture and boiled in a water bath for 20 min., cooled rapidly by immersion in cold water, and 1 mL of Nelson's solution was added. After the addition of Nelson's reagent, the mixture was shaken, and the solution was made up to 25 mL in a volumetric flask with distilled water. The optical density of the samples was measured on a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer at a wavelength of $\lambda = 610$ nm. When creating a calibration curve for determining the concentration of glucose in a glucose solution, D (optical density) values are entered on the X-axis, and concentration values are entered on the Y-axis. Samples were taken from the gastric juice of rabbit and chicken stomachs. Also, samples from the cellulose-feeding, bark-dwelling Corroid beetle and termites were cleaned with 3% hydrogen peroxide, alcohol, and distilled water. Cleaned samples were planted in meat peptone broth nutrient media prepared in laboratory conditions and placed in a thermostat with a temperature of 37 °C. Obtaining pure isolates of bacteria was done by the re-cultivation method generally accepted in microbiology in GPA nutrient medium. Bacteria with cellulolytic activity 1 from rabbit gastric juice, 1 from chicken glandular stomach, 1 from chicken gizzard, 1 from termite, 1 from cockroach, and 1 from goat gastric juice total (No. 1, 2, and 6). Six pure bacterial isolates were isolated. Bacteria belonging to the *Bacillus* genus are characterized by the fact that their spores are usually highly resistant to environmental influences, including exposure to UV rays, drying, and oxidizing agents such as hydrogen peroxide. Also, bacterial strains belonging to the *Bacillus* family isolated from the bark beetle (*Dendroctonus ponderosae*) and termites (*Coptotermes formosanus*) were genetically identified. *Bacillus subtilis* PBUZ-1.

Determination of cellulosic enzyme activity in selected bacterial strains

6 bacterial strains to determine cellulosic enzyme activity Sodium citrate-1,29 g/l; $\text{NH}_4\text{-}2$, $\text{HPO}_4\text{-}4,75$ g/l; $\text{KH}_2\text{ PO}_4\text{-}9,6$ g/l; and $\text{MgSO}_4\text{-}7 \text{ H}_2\text{O}\text{-}0,18$ g/l-were grown for 2 days in nutrient medium. 0.5% wheat bran and 0.5% carboxymethyl-cellulose (SM-Cellulose) were used as carbohydrate sources.

Figure 1. Cellulose activity of bacterial strains Bacillus

1-Bacillus was isolated from termites when the cellulolytic activity of bacterial strains was determined. sp. and isolated from goat gastric juice 4- B. subtilis strains with the highest activity were discovered. It was 0,233 and 0,193 TsIS/cm³. Positive results were obtained based on the catalase and gelatinase tests of two strains. The obtained results were processed using the Excel program. The arithmetic mean (M), standard deviation (m), and statistical reliability (R) were studied. Results lower than R0,05 were considered statistically reliable. Bacterial strains selected at the next stage of our research Sodium citrate (1,29 g/l), $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{ HPO}_4$ (4,75 g/l), $\text{KH}_2\text{ PO}_4$ (9,6 g/l), and $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7 \text{ H}_2\text{O}$ (0,18 g/l) were grown for 2 days in nutrient medium. 0.5% wheat bran and 0.5% carboxymethyl-cellulose (SM-Cellulose) were used as carbohydrate sources. Separate nutrient media were prepared for each carbohydrate source.

Table 1

Determination of cellulolytic activity of bacteria using DEAE-cellulose, units/ml.

№	Experience options	Substrates applied to nutrient media	
		Wheat bran (0,5%)	Carboxymethylcellulose (CM-Celluloz) (0,5%)
1	<i>Bacillus sp.1</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,295	0,196
2	<i>Bacillus sp.2</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,192	0,378
3	<i>Bacillus sp.3</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,255	0,185
4	<i>Bacillus sp.4</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,369	0,111
5	<i>Bacillus sp.5</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,727	0,478
6	<i>Bacillus sp.6</i> (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml bacterial fluid)	0,584	0,360

	fluid)		
7	Control feed environment (1ml 1ml Deae + 0.5 ml of feed environment)	0,163	0,330
8	Control water (1ml H ₂ O + 0.5 ml H ₂ O)	0,191	
9	Control Water (1ml DeE + 0.5 ml H ₂ O)	0,255	
10	Control Endo-1,3 (4) -b-GLUCANASE (1ml Deae + 0.5 ml Endo-1,3 (4) -b-glucanase)	0,217	

Necessary reagents: dinitrosalicylic reagent, 0.1 M, rN indicator 5,2, and phosphate-citrate buffer. Substrates: microcrystalline cellulose (Sigma-Aldrich, USA), DEAE-cellulose For the study, the cultured bacterial fluid on day 2 was filtered. 0,5 ml of each sample was taken, and 1 ml of DEAE M (dissolved in 0,05 g/10 ml of H₂O) was added and incubated on a shaker at 37 °C for 40 minutes. In order to stop the reaction, 0.5 ml of 96% ethyl alcohol was added to the experimental samples taken from the incubation. The 500-nm wavelength of the spectrophotometer was used to determine cellulolytic activity in selected bacterial strains. Cellulolytic activity of bacterial strains was determined using stained cellulose in the study. In experimental variants, cellulolytic activity is based on determining the degree of solubility of cellulose based on the methods of qualitative and quantitative determination of sugars. It made it possible to determine the activity of the cellulose complex using different soluble and insoluble substrates. When using soluble M-cellulose, the Cx-activity of the complex is determined. The M-cellulose activity of the bacteria selected for this study was determined because the linear region of hydrolysis of this substrate is limited. When determining the activity using insoluble cellulose, it is necessary to take into account the possible nonlinear dependence of the initial rate of cellulose hydrolysis on the substrate concentration. Control variants: 1 ml H₂O + 0,5 ml H₂O = 0,191 B/ml; control water: 1 ml DEAE + 0,5 ml H₂O = 0,255 B/ml; Control endo-1,3(4)--glucanase, 1 ml DEAE + 0,5 ml endo-1,3(4)--glucanase, was 0,217 B/ml, and control nutrient medium, 1 ml DEAE + 0.5 ml nutrient medium, was 0,163 B/ml, or 0,330 B/ml (Table 1). In the experiment, some bacterial strains showed activity when using a 5% (-M-cellulose) substrate, while others (0.5% wheat bran) showed activity. According to the results of the study, hen stars, gastric juice, local beetles, and termites have a cellulolytic activism. In the studies carried out, pure bacterial strains with cellulolytic activity were isolated and identified from the gastric juice of small ruminant goats, rabbits, chicken stomachs, bark beetles, and termites. Bacillus bacteria were screened for cellulase activity. The morphological characteristics of bacterial strains with high cellulase activity were studied. In our research, the determination of the cellulolytic activity of microorganisms isolated from ruminants and termites, which feed on roughage cellulose, served to create a new type of microbiological enzyme feed additives that involved the easy digestion of roughage in the veterinary field.

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